

Equilibrium between *n*-Propyl Alcohol, Propyl Ether and Water at 190°.

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No satisfactory data are available for the value of the equilibrium constants of organic reactions in the vapour phase even when reactions of compounds containing not more than three atoms of carbon in a molecule are considered. Amongst such reactions, the production of ethers by the dehydration of alcohols is the least complex and is important from both the technical and physico-chemical point of view. The reactions are :

The studies of equilibrium in reactions (i) and (ii) have already been reported by Jatkar and Watson and Gajendragad, Jatkar and Watson (*J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1126, **9A**, 99; 1932, **15A**, 59). The present investigation concerns itself with studies in equilibrium in reaction (iii).

Senderens (*Compt. rend.*, 1909, **148**, 227) prepared propyl ether by passing the vapours of *n*-propanol over alumina catalyst at 250°. Mailhe and Godon (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1920, **27**, 121) prepared *n*-propyl ether by passing the vapours of *n*-propyl alcohol over potassium alum dehydrated at 190°. The same reaction at 185°, produced an yield of propyl ether only 54.3% of the theoretical one. This value is considerably lower than the maximum amount obtained by us and the discrepancy is partly due to a faulty method of estimation of propyl ether employed by the authors and partly to the superior activity of our catalyst (*cf.* Jatkar and Watson, *loc. cit.*).

Studies in equilibrium of this reaction have not been done by any previous investigator and are therefore worth investigations from the theoretical point of view. It is also of technical importance since propyl ether is a good substitute for ethyl ether in industry, as the later being a gas in most parts of India is not of much use for industrial purposes.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Propyl alcohol used was distilled at 93.8° at 683 mm. $d_{20}^{20} = 0.8004$
 n_D at $27.2^{\circ} = 1.3835$. The same apparatus was used as has been
 described previously by Gajendragad, Jatkar and Watson (*loc. cit.*).

Analysis.—Difficulties were experienced in finding a satisfactory
 method of analysis of the mixture of propyl alcohol, propyl ether and
 water. The method finally adopted was essentially as follows. When
 the run was complete, the entire solution was poured into a 50 c.c.
 burette. The ether was separated by the addition of saturated salt
 solution and 50% sulphuric acid added to remove alcohol.

As the method involves loss of ether by vaporization and incom-
 plete separation, corrections must be made to obtain accurate
 results. In order to measure this loss, the volume of the compo-
 nents recoverable by this method from mixtures of known composition
 was determined. The corrections were plotted against the true
 volumes so that by means of the chart, true volume of ether in the
 mixture could be determined from the observed volume.

The solubility of the pure propyl ether in 50% sulphuric acid was
 determined with the following results:

- (1) Solubility of Pr_2O in H_2O is 0.1% by volume.
- (2) Solubility of H_2O in Pr_2O is 0.5% by volume.
- (3) Solubility of *n*-propyl ether in 50% sulphuric acid is 75%
 by volume.

Now starting with pure propyl alcohol and water, mixtures were
 prepared in a stoppered burette corresponding to various conversions
 of the propanol. The volume of water separating in each case was
 noted. Sodium chloride was added, the burette stoppered and shaken
 and the volumes of the two layers were noted again. The brine layer
 was separated out and an equal volume of 50% sulphuric acid (equal
 to the volume of upper layer) was added to the burette, which was
 then stoppered and shaken several times. The resulting volume of
 propyl ether (upper layer) is noted. From the observed volumes of
 propyl ether and the initial volume taken, a graph is plotted.

Starting with 25 c.c. of propyl alcohol, the theoretical volumes
 of the components at various % conversions are given below in
 columns A, B and C. The actual total volume of the mixture is
 given under I. The observed volume of the propyl ether separating
 is given under E and the correction for the observed volume of propyl
 ether for 25 c.c. of the total volume is given under F.

TABLE I.

	A	B	C	D	E	F
Corresponding % conversion.	Vol. of Pr ₂ O.	Vol. of PrOH	Vol. of H ₂ O.	Actual total vol. of the mixture.	Vol. of Pr ₂ O.	Correc- tion.
80	18.4	5.0	2.4	26.0	18.4	0.0
70	16.1	7.5	2.1	25.7	15.5	0.5
60	13.8	10.0	1.8	25.4	12.8	1.0
40	9.2	15.0	1.2	25.4	6.2	3.0

Thus in the case of 80% conversion, the observed volume of propyl ether is 18.4 for the total volume 26.0 and on reduction for 25 c.c. total volume, it becomes 17.6 c.c. The correction for the observed volume of propyl ether is then plotted against the reduced volume of 17.6 c.c. for 25 c.c. of the product. This graph is referred to in actual analysis of the product to determine the correction for the volume of propyl ether separating.

Procedure.—Propyl alcohol was run from a burette and the product was collected in exactly the same manner as was done in the case of experiments with methyl alcohol. All the runs taken consist of 25 c.c. of propyl alcohol. This quantity was necessary to reduce the error in the results. Increase in weight of the sulphuric acid bulb, represented the quantity of propylene evolved during the run.

The liquid products were weighed and transferred to a 50 c.c. stoppered gas burette and the volumes of the two layers were noted. The correction to the volume of propyl ether is read on the graph and added to the observed volume and the percentage conversions are calculated on this corrected volume of propyl ether.

The accuracy of the results depends upon the percentage conversions of propyl alcohol because of the large correction necessary at lower conversions. In the vicinity of the equilibrium point, the analysis is accurate within 1%. At and above 80% conversion, the separation of each of the components according to the above method is complete.

Experiments were made to determine the optimum temperature for the reaction. The rate of passage was kept constant at various temperatures and the product was analysed for propyl alcohol, propyl ether, propylene and water. Results are given below.

TABLE II.

Catalyst = Potassium alum (105 g.).

Expt. No.	Temp.	A PrOH converted to Pr ₂ O.	B PrOH converted to propylene.	PrOH decomposed. A + B
55-56	190°	69%	0.2%	60.8
53-54	200°	65	2.8	67.8
57-58	210°	75.6	5.0	80.6
59-60	220°	69.0	15.8	84.8
61-62	280°	55.4	28.6	84.0

In order to exclude the side-reaction, the catalyst has to be worked at 190°. Experiments were also tried at 185°, but as could be seen from the comparison of results in Table III, the velocity of reaction at 185° is far slower than the same at 190°.

TABLE III.

Catalyst = Potassium alum (105 g.).

Expt. No.	Temp.	Rate of PrOH in c.c. per hour.	Corrected vol. of Pr ₂ O.	PrOH converted to Pr ₂ O.
27	185°	0	31.1 c.c.	57%
28	185	20	14.2	62
29	185	20	11.2	55
30	185	20	12.1	58
31	185	10	15.9	69
32	185	10	15.4	67
33	185	5.5	17.4	75
34	185	6	17.5	76
35	190	6	18.0	78
36	190	10	17.4	78
37	190	20	15.0	85

The temperature 190° is therefore the optimum for the reaction. At temperatures higher than 190°, the side-reaction is appreciable, while at lower temperature the velocity of the reaction is slow.

Having determined the optimum temperature, experiments were made to determine the maximum yield of propyl ether. Runs were taken at slow rates over two samples of active catalyst. The results are given in Tables IV and V.

In the following table, the composition of the product in volumes as observed, is given in columns 4, 5 and 6. In the 7th column, the percentage of propyl ether is given and the percentage of propylene amongst the products is shown in the last column.

Experiment No. 43 onwards are the results obtained by passing a mixture $\text{Pr}_2\text{O} - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and under K_p are given the calculated values of

$$\frac{C_{\text{Pr}_2\text{O}} \times C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{C_{\text{PrOH}}^2}$$

TABLE IV.

Catalyst = Fresh active potash alum (100 g.). Temp. = 190°.

Expt. No.	Total wt. of product.	Rate.	Composition of product in volume.			% Conv.	C_3H_6 .
			Pr_2O .	PrOH .	H_2O .		
38	20.58	30 c.c.	16.0 c.c.	7.4 c.c.	1.56 c.c.	70.9	0.2%
39	21.18	30	17.1	8.0	1.60	70.1	„
40	20.67	10	17.6	5.4	2.30	76.2	„
41	20.39	12	18.8	4.5	2.45	79.3	„
42	20.33	8.5	19.5	3.1	3.00	82.9	„

TABLE V.

Catalyst = Fresh potash alum (100 g.). Temp. = 190°.

Expt. No.	Total wt. of distillate.	Rate.	Composition of product in mols. %			% Conv. Pr_2O	C_3H_6 .	K_p .
			PrOH .	H_2O .	Pr_2O .			
47	17.38	7.5 c.c.	13.03	46.8	40.1	82.2	1.1%	11
48	18.00	8.6	14.80	22.1	41.5	82.0	0.6	8
49	18.58	6.5	12.10	47.1	40.7	83.6	1.6	13
50	18.68	6.0	13.20	46.4	40.4	84.1	1.6	10
51	19.78	11.0	15.20	42.8	41.9	82.2	1.1	8

The reverse reaction was studied with the following arrangement of apparatus. Propyl ether was dropped under a controlled rate from the burette into a bulb wherein it was vapourised, then the vapours were allowed to be saturated with water in the copper saturator and finally the vapours were freed from spray by the trap. The bulb, copper saturator and the trap were completely immersed in a thermostat at 88°–89°. The vapours, thus saturated, were then passed through the apparatus and the product was analysed for propyl ether, propyl alcohol, water and propylene as in the direct runs.

TABLE VI.

Reverse reaction on the same catalyst.

Expt. No	Total wt. of product.	Rate.	Composition of product in volume.				
			Pr ₂ O.	PrOH.	H ₂ O.	Pr ₂ O.	C ₃ H ₆ .
43	16.60	4.4 g.	16.5 c.c.	2.22 c.c.	2.22 c.c.	39.0%	0.1%
44	16.51	2.0	16.8	2.40	1.80	87.3	„
45	18.20	6.0	18.1	2.55	2.48	88.4	„

DISCUSSION.

If the percentage conversions given in Table IV are plotted against the rates, the curve cuts the zero rate at 84% conversions. The equilibrium constant corresponding to this value is about $K_p = 8$. If values of K_p as calculated from the results of the reverse reactions given in Table VI, are plotted against the rates, the extrapolation gives the value of $K_p = 8$.

By starting with a fresh sample of the active catalyst, we could actually get 84% conversion as in Table IV, Expt. 50.

Experiments were incidentally undertaken to study the mechanism of catalytic dehydration. Although there is a large volume of similar work of Sabatier and his school of workers, no exhaustive study of particular cases has so far been made. It is usually assumed that the dehydration occurs in two steps:

the second reaction predominating at higher temperatures.

In the case of ethyl alcohol Senderen (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1912. *viii*, 25, 505) believes that the formation of ether and ethylene from alcohol are two independent reactions. He found that at 250°, the rate of decomposition of pure ether to give ethylene is many times greater than the rate of formation of ethylene from alcohol and with some catalysts and other alcohols, the formation of ether was insignificant. Ether may not be therefore be an intermediate product in the dehydration. The following experiments point to similar conclusion in the case of propyl alcohol, propyl ether having been found to be more stable than propyl alcohol under the action of catalyst.

TABLE VII.

Decomposition of propyl ether.

Expt. No.	Temp.	Rate.	% Conv. to C ₂ H ₄ .
63	230°	10 c.c.	46·7
64	230	5	67·5
65	230	10	46·7
66	210	10	46·9
67	190	10	1·2
68	190	10	0·4

Experiments 63-68 were made by passing propyl ether over the catalyst. The results when compared with Table I bring out the comparative stability of ether compared with alcohol when allowance is made for the catalyst being engaged in decomposing the alcohol. Further it was found that part of propyl ether was converted to propyl alcohol, the reverse reaction taking place with the water formed by decomposition of ether.

The following experiments 69 to 71 were then undertaken to find the extent of decomposition by passing mixtures of propyl alcohol and propyl ether. In order to have the same time of contact, this mixture was passed at twice the rate of pure ether was passed. If we assume that propylene comes from propyl ether then we ought to get two molecules of propylene to one molecule of water. On the other hand propyl alcohol on decomposition would give propylene and water in the ratio of one to one. The results show that the latter relation holds good. Further propyl ether does not affect the direct dehydration of propyl alcohol to propylene.

TABLE VIII

Rate = 20 c.c. an hour. Temperature = 230°.

Expt. No.	Composition of initial mixture.		Composition of final mixture.			
	Pr ₂ O.	PrOH.	Propylene.	H ₂ O.	Pr ₂ O.	PrOH.
69	7.55 g.	4.45 g.	1.84 g.	1.75 g.	7.00 g.	1.40 g.
70	7.50	5.89	3.14	1.55	7.55	1.16
71	9.33	5.51	3.90	1.75	7.40	1.40

SUMMARY.

1. The equilibrium in the reaction $2n\text{PrOH} \rightleftharpoons n\text{Pr}_2\text{O} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 190° corresponds to 84% conversion of the alcohol.

2. Propyl ether cannot be the intermediate product in the dehydration of propyl alcohol to propylene because propyl ether is found to be far more stable than propyl alcohol to the action of potassium alum catalyst.

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